

Quantum Interference and Point Versus Interval? Part 2

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Quantum mechanics is well known for its probability density $W^*(x)W(x)$ which appears in descriptions of 2-slit interference and bound states etc. Here we argue that the spatial density in x is due to the possibility of at least two different momenta at the same x point. We consider the case of 2-slit interference and bound states and their relation to Newtonian mechanics.

Free Particle Probability

In Newtonian mechanics, one describes a free particle by $x=vt$ (moving in the x direction), but if there is an elastic collision between two particles, energy and momentum are conserved. This means that given an e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 (vectors), there will be outcome vectors. In general, however, it may not be easy to determine what these values are, even if they conform with conservation. As a result, we have suggested that one introduce a free particle probability, even in Newtonian mechanics. To allow for conservation of energy and momentum without giving any real value weight to a free particle (there is no energy distribution for example), we proposed:

$$\exp(i C_1 e) \text{ and } \exp(i C_2 p) \quad ((1))$$

The problem with ((1)) is that p and $-p$ (one dimension) have different values when they should have the same value. Thus, one needs to introduce a measure which changes sign when the x axis changes direction. We suggest using $\exp(i p \delta x)$. At this point, one may make the probability Lorentz invariant and use:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((2))$$

This is a complex probability, but should behave in AND and OR situations in the same manner as usual probability. We try to consider the effects of this probability on spatial density.

We first note that $\exp(ipx)$ introduces uncertainty in space of the order:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((3))$$

To see this spatial uncertainty in another context, one may consider the case in which momentum in a 2-body collision is not conserved.

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_3x-ip_4x) \exp(ip_1x+ip_2x) = 0 \text{ for } p_3+p_4 \neq p_1+p_2 \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one requires some length of space to obtain 0, one does obtain this result at a point.

Two Slit Interference

As noted in Part 1, interference in a 2-slit problem occurs because one is forced to use probability because there is uncertainty in space of \hbar/p and so if the slit widths are roughly of this length, one cannot ascertain through which slit the particle passes. It will pass through one, but there are probabilities for interactions with both slits before an actual interaction occurs and the particle passes through one slit. This leads to an:

$$\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2) \quad \text{OR scenario} \quad ((5))$$

Here \mathbf{r}_1 is the vector from the center of the first slit to a point on a screen far away and \mathbf{r}_2 from the center of the second slit to the same point. Mathematically, one has 0 values of ((5)) at certain theta points, with theta being the same for both slits in the far away screen approximation, i.e. for \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 being parallel vectors. In particular:

$$d \sin(\theta) = (n + \frac{1}{2}) \hbar/p \quad ((6)) \quad d = \text{slit separation}$$

Here, we note that $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ has unit modulus for any point along x or along the vector \mathbf{r} . This means that one may use $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ in a 2-body collision probability calculation at any point with the same probability as it represents a single probability. With OR situations, one has at least two different momenta. In this approximation:

$$\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1 = p r_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2 = p (r_1 + b) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where } b = d \sin(\theta) \quad ((7))$$

One may ask: Can ((5)) be represented by: $B \exp(i f(p, r))$? To test this, one may multiply ((5)) by its complex conjugate:

$$2 + 2 \cos(pb) \quad \text{where } b = d \sin(\theta) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the answer is no.

Different theta values (i.e. different points on the screen) have different values for ((5)) because two different momenta (vectors not magnitude) are present at the same point. We argue that quantum spatial density is due to the interference meaning an OR situation of different momenta at the same point and the $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ form of probability.

Quantum Bound State

A classical bound state, in the time-independent approximation, is described by:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(x) + V(x) \psi(x) = E \psi(x) \quad ((9))$$

Time is not separated here, but either $v(x)$ or $-v(x)$ applies at each x point, but not both at the same time.

In the quantum case, one needs to describe interactions with $V(x)$ and either $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ for any p may apply. The point is that unlike Newtonian mechanics, one does not have conservation of energy and momentum in a tiny dx about the point x . As a result, all $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are used or:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((10)) \text{ and}$$

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad \hbar=1 \quad ((11))$$

One may note that for any energy level, ((11)) may be written as:

$$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{Thus, } KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad ((13))$$

((13)), however, uses all $\exp(ipx)$ pairs and is an average. ((13)) holds for all energy levels, but in the high energy level limit, quantum mechanics should seemingly look like classical mechanics. We ask: What is happening?

If one considers $p_{rms}(x)$ for a low energy level, where $KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m$, then $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ does not fit in a small dx about x . We have pointed this out in previous notes. Here, we suggest that the real problem with this is that one cannot have conservation of energy and momentum within this tiny dx about x and this is what makes the quantum result differ from the classical, even though the form ((12)) (which holds for both) and for all energy levels is the same. It is the notion of a lack of energy and momentum conservation in dx which separates the quantum case from the classical and this is then due to multiple p values at the same x and hence a density in space, instead of $\exp(ipx)$.

What happens as the energy level becomes very high? In such a case, $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ fits in a tiny dx about x (even several wavelengths) may fit and so one may have conservation of energy and momentum using the wavefunction $\exp(i p_{rms}(x) x)$. In such a case, one has a clear sense of direction and a single value of p (name either $p_{rms}(x)$ or $-p_{rms}(x)$). One sees classical Newtonian mechanics emerge, we argue. It is the notion of $\exp(ipx)$'s and their relation to conservation of momentum in collisions such that outcome pairs p_x, k (from $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$) such that $\exp(i(p+k)x)$ is indistinguishable (even though V_k is not) for all $p+k =$ number cases, which governs interactions. If this gives rise to the notion of a sharp $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ within a little dx , then one may use this single value as conforming to conservation of energy and momentum within that little region dx , we argue.

We note that in the bound case, spatial density, and in fact 0 points of $W(x)$ are due to including p and $-p$ pairs. As noted, in the high energy limit, one may have either $p_{rms}(x)$ or $-p_{rms}(x)$ in each dx region and so one is not forced to have both. This suggests that one cannot consider that $W(x)=0$ points mean that a particle cannot be at such a point. Rather, they show resolution in space in the bound state case. If one knocks out the bound particle and notes its

unique p value, then it is linked with $\exp(ipx)$ which could have come from any x point, including $W(x)=0$ points.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the free particle probability $\exp(i p x)$ which ensures that any p_{xi} , p_{xj} values such that $p_{xi}+p_{xj}=p_{x1}+p_{x2}$ for initial p_{x1}, p_{x2} have the same product probability ensures that OR situations of mixed probabilities leads to spatial density. This appears in the 2-slit case and bound states. We suggest that in the bound state case, having $\hbar/p_{rms}(x)$ fit in dx means that one may establish conservation of energy and momentum in this tiny dx and this is what gives rise to classical Newtonian mechanics.